

Taking Heidegger Literally: A Brief Note

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Abstract

This note argues that Heidegger's account of the *Lichtung* should be taken more literally than Heidegger himself allows. Heidegger shows us that beings are not first encountered neutrally but rather in a meaningful world. Yet by treating the clearing as an ontological condition rather than the already-open world itself, Heidegger preserves a metaphysical residue. Against this, I read the clearing as literal: sky, ground, horizon, the already-around-us. This literalization exposes what I believe to be the agrarian limits of Heidegger's grammar of Being, ground, dwelling and rootedness. Instead I will borrow from a language with less agrarian-echos, Turkish, and reinterpret the term *Yol* to mean the "way", as we often study things in terms of the way they are, this is often taken for granted. From here I do a very minimal introduction to *yolcu* and attempt to analyze what it may offer over *Dasein*. This note is preliminary and an early gathering of thoughts that I have towards this project. I plan on developing it much further, in time.

1 Introduction

Heidegger's breakthrough was to show that we do not first neutrally encounter beings, we encounter them entangled in a web of meaning/context. The hammer example by Heidegger shows us that a hammer is not first seen as an object to measure before use but is disclosed through its very use, it is for-hammering.

A person does not stand outside of the world as a detached subject observing objects, the person is already-involved in a meaningful world. Heidegger shows

us that the separation between beings (Seiendes) and Being (Sein) is essential. Heidegger claims that Being is not like beings, it is not an object, rather it is the clearing by which beings can be disclosed as beings. Heidegger gives us the image of the *lichtung* (clearing-in-the-forest) but does not want us to take it literally, instead he wishes to convey that light is not shone onto beings in a clearing because of the clearing itself but rather because the clearing allows it to occur at all. I will proceed to take Heidegger literally to see where it takes us.

2 Yol: The Lichtung Already-Around Us

I read Heidegger in-tandem with the Orkhon-inscriptions, these are 8th century Nomadic-Turkic inscriptions carved into rock. They detail the political lives of the Turkic-Nomads of the time, politics did not simply mean *how to run a state*, to the Nomads politics was the embodiment of everyday life, it was practical. These inscriptions offer an insight into the worldview of nomadic-peoples that Heidegger simply does not recover, Heidegger speaks of the black forest, he speaks of rootedness and dwelling not of wandering. He reduces things to questioning and answering rather than letting them stay as wonder. Most importantly, Heidegger views the *world* in an agrarian manner, I take *world* to be Heidegger's *Being-in-the-world* to say that Heidegger can imagine the pre-metaphysical, practical and entangled web of meaning for *Dasein* but he cannot escape reducing Being to a question whose answer must be sought.

The Turkic nomads speak of *Yol*, this translates today as way/path/road/journey, this is the modern cut of the word but to the nomads it meant something not more grand but rather more practical. *Yol* named a way-of-life, a way-of-being but in Turkish it escapes needing to be a way-of or a way-to, it remains *Way* in a fundamental sense. I will use *Yol* to mean, in the broadest sense, *Way*, then everything becomes an analysis of *The way anything comes underway*. I mean underway more in the sense of *the-way-it-is* rather than as under-way to mean that *Yol* is a higher metaphysical entity. To the nomads, the importance of sky, ground, and horizon cannot be understated. It is the sky that grants day and rain, the ground that provides grass for livestock, and the horizon

that provides for security, openness, room-to-wander, and room-to-wonder. I had Heidegger's concept of the *lichtung* stuck in my head, I wondered what a conversation between these nomads and Heidegger would've been like, but I started coming to the conclusion that the nomads already had a practical "in-hand" sense of *lichtung*, it was simply *already-all-around*. Heidegger claims to surpass old metaphysical attempts at describing reality and of course in many ways he does, but his non-literality of *lichtung* seems as if to hide what is plainly there. Here Turkish becomes useful again, Turkish is an agglutinative language and so it builds off of a mother-word.

So I will then suggest the word "yolcu", in modern Turkish it means traveller/wanderer, I will take this to mean *underway* or *on-the-way* as it seems most fitting to its relation to "Way". So what if instead of *Dasein* we submit the analytic of *yolcu*, what would change? *Dasein* is the translation of the German *Being-there*, it is Heidegger's redefinition of the human hoping to strip away any extra baggage of biology, psychology, or detached-subjecthood. *Dasein* is the one already entangled in a world-of-meaning. *Yolcu* can be similar in this sense, it includes temporality as it is and it also gives us an entangled-human, this time without the worry of "being", "becoming" or "there" to complicate the term requiring further definition. A human as "on-the-way" is weak if we take it only in English, the point is that *yolcu* manages to give us an analytic for the human-being as already-underway/on-the-way. This affords temporality, it affords care because it was *shared* into a way-of-being where it cannot remain static.

3 From Clearing to Way

The task is not to recover Being, the task is to stop treating the open as if it were hidden. If the clearing is already the world around us, then beings do not need to be explained by a condition of disclosure. They are already-there, already-in-the-open. They already move, stand, relate. The question is not what hidden Being allows them to appear but what way they are already underway.

We must also rethink the analytic of the human. *Dasein* is the being for

whom Being is an issue. Yolcu is not defined by the baggage of questioning Being, yolcu is the one already underway/on-the-way. I do not mean this as traveller or passenger, I mean it to say that human existence is never static or neutral, it is always from-somewhere, toward-somewhere, amongst, under-sky, above-ground. We find ourselves in an open steppe, already shared, already underway. Temporality and care are thus not "deep" conditions of *being-underway* but rather included neatly within being *underway*.

Yol is not a Turkish translation of Heidegger's concept of Being. Rather, it is the refusal to allow for a deeper problem at all. Before a "deeper problem" must be revealed, yolcu must be underway-to-undertake, it is this *wayness* that I attend to with Yol.

It also makes the question-itself fundamentally too late, a question is an undertaking, it is a way of language. To ask the question-itself, one does not need to have a *pre-ontological* understanding, it must simply be underway to worry about way-at-all. This keeps philosophy more practical than Heidegger affords himself. It keeps thought close to the opened-world already-here instead of lifting the openness of that world into an ontological register.